

NIGHT OWLS – THE “B” PEOPLE

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If you find it hard to get up in the morning, don't despair - you're not lazy, you're just genetically programmed that way, says the B-Society by Chris Morris (2007). A night owl is person who tends to stay up until late at night, and the opposite of night owl is an early bird, a lark, someone who tends to begin sleeping at a time that is considered early and also wakes early. . In many countries, early birds are called "A-people" and night owls are called "B-people." Some of us are clearly "larks" -early risers-while others of us are diversely night owls. The rest of us fall more or less in between the two. In study magazine, reported that IQ average and sleeping patterns are most definitely related, proving that those who play under the moon are, indeed, more intelligent human beings said Satoshi Kanazawa (2010), a psychologist at the London School of Economics and Political Science.

Night Owls Have More Stamina

Stamina in terms of across the board axis. Research has shown that night owls can remain focused on tasks at hand longer and better than their morning lark counterparts.

They Are More Open Minded

Things that happen at night are things you can't get away with during the day. It's the time of booming passionate, underhanded trade and unseemly professions. It's when the bars are opened and the poets write. It's when musicians pour over instruments, geniuses have their refinements and artists come alive. They would probably be good at cryptic crosswords. There are things to be explored at night that early risers will never witness. There are ideas articulated and tasks completed that early risers never get to finish. Their minds are freer to roam and think at night when people are asleep and when you are not absorbing their anxious energy (which deters the natural thinking mind). Average brains are conditioned to follow this sleep pattern, while the more curious, geeky ones want to mock that pattern and create their own.

They Are Prone to be Risk Takers:

This current entrepreneurial age is the perfect time to be a risk-taker. With so much competition they have to be a little different to stand out from the rest of the crowd. Luckily for night owls, they are unlike and tend to be bigger risk-takers compared to morning people. Psychologists have found that those who stayed up later tend to have a higher sense of entitlement and seemed to be more exploitative. Evening types were more extroverted, more people-oriented.

Teenagers and Night Owls:

School-age children are commonly early birds, while teenagers tend to be night owls, and then as they age, adults gradually transition back into morning people." A recent study in Belgium found that night owls are able to stay more focused as the day goes on, compared with early risers. There late nights are partly biologically driven. Hormonal changes during puberty affect the body's internal clock, which means most high schoolers -- even

ones who used to be early risers -- tend to stay up well after dark and sleep until noon.

They Make More Money

According to a research at the University of Madrid (2013), because of their higher IQs, creative and risk-taking competencies, it makes sense that night owls also tend to earn large incomes. This may be the reason why some of the most successful people are night owls.

Stay-up-late types, according to research, attain greater financial and professional success on average than those people with earlier bedtimes and wake times. President Barack Obama is reputed to a night owl as was Charles Darwin, Adolf Hitler, Keith Richards, Marcel Proust, Elvis Presley and James Joyce. Other night owls such as the former US President Bill Clinton, and the former British Prime Minister Winston Churchill. Some studies have shown that people who stay up late are more productive than early risers, and have more stamina around the length of their days. On the other hand research indicates that people who stay up late are at higher risk for depression. Night owls tend to be prone to a host of different health and mood disorders, involving just a general sense of mental instability; however, depression was by far the most common shared trait next to obesity. Studies have also shown night owls are more prone to more significant tobacco and alcohol use, as well as inclined to additional eating, and also less healthy diets than early risers or people with intermediate sleep patterns. But research on the impact of chronotype isn't all bad news for night owls. Other research has shown that night owls display greater reasoning and analytical abilities than their earlier-to-bed counterparts.

Psychologists have found that people who are constantly described as "night owls" display more signs of egocentrism, Machiavellianism and psychopathic tendencies than those who are "morning larks". Morning people, however, also have upper hand. "Larks typically sleep better, have more periodic sleep patterns, and have more flexible personalities," said Sharkey (2012). They also tend to be happier and feel healthier than B people, according to a recent study from the University of Toronto. Famous morning larks embrace Napoleon, Ernest Hemingway and George W Bush.

CONCLUSION:

Night owls perform better than early risers at inductive reasoning and demonstrate a greater capacity to think conceptually as well as analytically. On the other hand, night owls should take advantage of their nocturnal productivity, and think about alterable businesses that are suitable for them to be the happiest, healthiest owl they can be. I think it's more about taking the time away from noise, away from draining society, away from other people and most do this at night. I doubt one's socio-economic status is an indicator of a lower or higher IQ. Studies showed that limiting nighttime exposure to artificial light and increasing exposure to daytime sunlight can shift sleep-wake cycles earlier. The moon is enchanted, however, you can also dance under the

sun. Both have jolting energy....isn't it all about balance?

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